

Melting points of the compounds were uncorrected and the purity was checked by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (DMSO- d_6 ; TMS as internal standard) on a FX 90Q JEOL spectrometer (90 MHz).

Results and Discussion

All the pyrido[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines are yellow coloured, high melting solids and showed ir bands at 3 380–3 340 (NH), 3 120–3 110br (C=NH), 1 195–1 185 strong (C=S) and three bands at 1 585–1 430 cm^{-1} (NH–C=S). The nmr spectra showed the resonance of the NH and C=NH protons in the range δ 7.83–9.08, multiplet at δ 6.50–8.34 due to the aromatic protons, and a singlet at δ 3.82–3.86 due to OCH_3 protons. The CH_2 protons of ethoxy group occurred as a quartet at δ 4.12–4.15 and CH_3 protons as a triplet at δ 1.40–1.44. The ir and nmr spectral data are recorded in Table 2.

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Synthesis of 2-(4'-Nitroanilino)-4-(2'-carbamoylphenoxy)-6-(arylthioureido)-*s*-triazine Derivatives as Antibacterial Agents

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THIUREA derivatives possess wide therapeutic activities¹. Salicylamide exhibits strong antipyretic, antispasmodic and sedative actions². Moreover salicylamide has marked analgesic property. Phenoxyethers of *s*-triazine are well known fungicides³ and potential therapeutic agents⁴.

Anticipating that the combined presence of N–C=S and 2-carbamoylphenoxy groupings in an *s*-triazine nucleus may enhance antibacterial

activity, we have synthesised 2-(4'-nitroanilino)-4-(2'-carbamoylphenoxy)-6-(arylthioureido)-*s*-triazine derivatives (1).

Cyanuric chloride and *p*-nitroaniline in equimolar proportions were condensed. The intermediate so obtained was reacted with salicylamide, followed by reaction with various arylthiourea to get the corresponding *s*-triazine derivatives (1).

Experimental

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

2-(4'-Nitroanilino)-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine: To a stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (1.84 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone at 0–5°, a solution of *p*-nitroaniline (1.39 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone was added. The reaction mixture was stirred at 0–5° for 2 h maintaining neutral pH. It was then poured into crushed ice, and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from alcohol, (90%), m.p. 290°.

2-(4'-Nitroanilino)-4-(2'-carbamoylphenoxy)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine: To a stirred solution of 2-(4'-nitroanilino)-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine (2.86 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone at 35°, was added a solution of salicylamide (1.37 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone over a period of 0.5 h. The temperature was gradually raised to 45° during 2 h with stirring and maintaining a neutral pH. It was then poured onto crushed ice, and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from alcohol, (76%), m.p. 300°.

General method for preparation of 2-(4'-nitroanilino)-4-(2'-carbamoylphenoxy)-6-(arylthioureido)-*s*-triazine (1): A mixture of 2-(4'-nitroanilino)-4-(2'-carbamoylphenoxy)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine (3.87 g, 0.01 mol) and arylthiourea (0.01 mol) in acetone was refluxed for 3 h on a water-bath. It was then treated with crushed ice, and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from alcohol (Table 1): ν_{max} 820–830 (*s*-triazine), 1 265–1 270 (C–O–C), 1 470–1 480 (C–N thiourea), 3 400–3 415 (NH) and 1 615–1 620 cm^{-1} (NHCO).

The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* at a concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹ using agar-plate method⁵. Amongst the compounds (Table 1) tested, compound sl. no. 9 showed maximum activity (zone of inhibition 2 and 2.5 mm) and that sl. no. 4 showed minimum activity (zone of inhibition 1.0 and 0.5 mm) against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* respectively.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1*

Sl. no.	Ar	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	C ₆ H ₅	120	51
2.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	123	59
3.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	191	54
4.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	174	60
5.	<i>o</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	178	47
6.	<i>m</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	181	52
7.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	249	54
8.	<i>o</i> -O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄	152	61
9.	<i>m</i> -O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄	149	68
10.	<i>p</i> -O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄	181	80

* All compounds showed correct results of elemental analysis for nitrogen.

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Synthesis of some Derivatives of Diaryl-substituted Pyrazole and Isoxazole and Substituted Chromenopyrazoline and Chromenoisoxazoline

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PYRAZOLE and isoxazole derivatives possess diverse biological activities¹. In view of these important medicinal properties, we report here the synthesis of some new derivatives 4-benzoyloxy-2-hydroxy-dibenzoylmethane² (**1**) has been condensed separately with hydrazine, phenylhydrazine and hydroxyl-

amine (Scheme 1). The product of condensation with hydrazine has been shown to be **2** from nmr data, which showed nine protons in the aromatic region of which the sharp singlet at δ 7.05 correspond to pyrazole ring proton. There were no signals from the benzoyl moiety which is presumed to have undergone hydrolysis. The structure was supported by mass spectral data which showed peaks at m/z 252, 135, 103 and 77.

The phenyl hydrazine condensation product **3** retained the benzoic ester moiety, and its structure has been deduced from ir and mass spectral data, m/z 180. The isoxazole derivatives (**4**) might be a mixture of two regioisomers **4a** and **4b**, or only one of these, but it could not be established. The mass spectrum of the compound showed peaks at m/z 105 corresponding to C₆H₅CO⁺ and at m/z 137 corresponding to dihydroxy benzoyl cation which can only originate from **4a** and **4b**. 4,4'-Dimethoxy-2'-hydroxychalcone (**5**), prepared from resacetophenone-4-methyl ether, was also condensed with hydrazine and hydroxylamine to give the corresponding pyrazoline (**6**) and dihydroisoxazole (**7**).

In the pyrazoline derivative (**6**), the aliphatic protons formed an ABX pattern with AB part appearing as 8 lines centred at δ 3.4 while the X part appeared as 3 lines centred at δ 4.8. The mass spectrum showed besides the molecular ion peak at m/z 298, prominent peaks at m/z 191, 175, 150, 149 and 134.

In the isoxazole derivative (**7**) the aliphatic protons formed an AMX pattern giving three one-proton double-doublets centred at δ 2.7, 3.6 and 5.0. The mass spectrum showed besides M^+ peak at 299, prominent peaks at m/z 282, 134 and 121. 3-Carboethoxy-7,8-dimethoxy-4-hydroxycoumarin (**8**), made from gallacetophenone dimethyl ether and diethyl carbonate in the presence of sodium, was also condensed separately with hydrazine hydrate and hydroxylamine hydrochloride. The product from the former was formulated as **9** incorporating a chromone moiety and a fused pyrazolone moiety. The product from hydroxylamine condensation was formulated as **10** having a chromone moiety and a fused isoxazolone system. Both the structures have been supported by nmr and ir data. The ir spectra showed a chromone carbonyl at 1605 and 1620 cm⁻¹ respectively in compounds **9** and **10**.

Experimental

All m.ps. were taken in a paraffin-bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Hitachi 270-30 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Jeol JNM-FX100 FT spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-D300 spectrometer. Tlc was performed in TEF (toluene-ethyl formate-formic acid, 5 : 4 : 1). Micro-analysis data were within $\pm 0.4\%$ of the theoretical values.

4-Benzoyloxy-2-hydroxydibenzoylmethane (**1**): Resacetophenone dibenzoate² (3.0 g) dissolved in